

ADABIYOTDA VERJINIYA VULF QARASHLARI

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada iste'dodli yozuvchi Verjiniya Vulf va uning qarashlariga munosabat bildirilgan. Ijodkorning jahon adabiyoti taraqqiyotiga qo'shgan hissasi, asarlarining mavzu-mundariyasi keng tarzda yoritib berilgan. Nazariy qarashlarga munosabat bildirilgan.

Tayanch so'zlar: tushuncha, badiiy olam, nazariy poetika, qalb dialektikasi, tahlil, talqin, tamoyil, syujet va kompozitsiya.

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Аннотация: В статье речь идет о талантливой писательнице Вирджинии Вульф и ее взглядах. Широко освещены вклад художника в развитие мировой литературы, предметное содержание его произведений. Выражены реакции на теоретические взгляды.

Ключевые слова: концепт, взаимность, художественный мир, теоретическая поэтика, диалектика души, анализ, интерпретация, принцип, сюжет и композиция.

Abstract: The article deals with the talented writer Virginia Woolf and her views. The artist's contribution to the development of world literature, the subject-content of his works are widely covered. Reactions to theoretical views are expressed.

Key words: concept, reciprocity, artistic world, theoretical poetics, dialectics of soul, analysis, interpretation, principle, plot and composition.

Looking for different ways to reflect the depths of the human soul in the art of words, even when observing various currents such as romanticism, then classicism, enlightenment in Europe, modernism, postmodernism and checking the literature of today's globalization, the research of the psyche gradually deepens and explores the female heart. We can see that the development is getting stronger and stronger. In the literature of the new era, it is possible to witness that looking at a woman through a women eyes has risen to a new level, and new pages have been opened in the book of literature. We can consider this only in the example of Virginia Woolf works on literature and literary studies.

The observation of "women literature" led to the approval of the term "women literary studies". This science is still under development. English writer Virginia Woolf made a significant contribution to women's literary studies.

Virginia Woolf is a bright representative of 20 th century modernist literature (Virginia Woolf, 1882-1941) critics divide his work into three stages. "The Voyage Out" in the first

stage, "Night and Thursday" the stories included in the collection, in many ways, became the result of research in the early stages of the artist's work and synthesized the specific features of the style in the spirit of impressionism, and also determined the prospects for further development "Jacob's Room" the novel was created. The second stage belongs to the mid-1920s, which is the peak of Woolf's creativity "Mrs. Dalloway" "To the Lighthouse" novels are written. In the third stage "Orlando", "The Waves", "The Years", "Between the Acts" whose novels have seen the world. In addition, Woolf wrote many articles on literature and painting. His "The Common Reader", collection, defender of women's rights "A Room of One's Own" At the time of his essay, he gained high attention. In the next essay, Woolf focuses on issues such as the role of women in the family and society, the role of women in raising children, women's perception of the world, and the relationship between modern men and women.

The basis of Virginia Woolf's novels is the search for "life", that is, the beginning corresponding to the ideal artistic-aesthetic form of storytelling. According to Virginia Woolf's, "life" is manifested in the form of consciousness, death and time. Indeed, Virginia Woolf's novels are an important part of modernist literature, and they were considered masterpieces of their time. In our opinion, they differ sharply from other novels and are built on the basis of a unique aesthetic law, that is, the law of integrity. In contrast to modern novels, charm, wonder and magical power prevail in them. The poetics of prose speech, which was used in the works of contemporary writers, took a new form in the novels of the poets, reached artistic color and rose. Looking at world literature of the 20th century, there is no doubt about Virginia Woolf's contribution to the breadth of creativity and the development of modernist literature.

Virginia Woolf, a follower of Joyce and theoretician of modernism, in her articles opposed the supporters of realism of her time, tending to interpret them as "fleeting", "absurd", "remarkable" events in their inability to distinguish between the "most important" and "real" things in human life. accused. He deeply mastered the philosophy of Henri Bergson, and was his loyal follower. In Woolf's imagination, the things hidden in the depths of the human mind and subconsciousness are "real", and "transitory" and "nonsensical" events are social connections and relationships, because they do not have "eternal" value. Of course, this was a subjective, one-sided worldview. His first work is "The Voyage Out" and the later ones have no plot, not even a connecting story line. They were just images that reflected the inner states of various characters in the style of impressionism, experiences consisting of a stream of consciousness. The term stream of consciousness was first used by Woolf. Virginia Woolf relied on the works of Marcel Proust in his literary style and literary outlook.

Men literature and women literature seem to be mutually exclusive concepts, but they have a number of unique aspects. First of all, this is related to the attitude towards the subject, which aspects of it are paid attention to, in general, in the interpretation typical of men or women - because the issue of accepting the world, interfering with objective reality, approaching it emotionally or intellectually is definitely not the same for both genders.

In optics, the ability to record the captured image of the lens better or worse is expressed by the concept of "light power". In our opinion, it gives the impression that women's literature acts as such a "power of light" in showing the temperature level of feelings, heartbreaks from

pain, extremely delicate and extremely complex processes of relations between women and the world. .

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